
A NEW APPROACH FOR DETERMINING OPTIMAL REGULARIZATION PARAMETER IN NEAR-FIELD ACOUSTIC HOLOGRAPHY FOR EFFECTIVE LOCALIZATION AND QUANTIFICATION OF ACOUSTIC SOURCE

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Acoustic holography is widely used in automobile, aerospace and defense applications for correctly pinpointing noise sources. It also helps in characterizing noise regions of interest in terms of frequency and amplitude level to understand its dominance. In recent years, Near-field Acoustic Holography (NAH) technique has gained more importance among other acoustic localization techniques since it captures rapidly decaying evanescent waves in near-field of source thus producing a high resolution source image. Hence high resolution localization of nearby sources is easily possible using NAH but quantification of the source is a concern due to inversion of evanescent waves which is focused upon in this work. The amplitude quantification of source is an issue in general when dealing with inverse problems. In NAH, the ill-conditioning of data matrix occurs leading to amplification of source levels because data on measurement plane is back propagated towards source plane. The noise associated smaller singular values tend to amplify and burst-off the solution when measurement plane data is inverted. Hence a k-space low pass filter called Tikhonov Regularization is used to suppress the high wavenumber noise components from data matrix to avoid amplification of source levels. The level of filtering to be done is also an important aspect since too much filtering would tend to affect localization by smoothing the solution and too less filtering would lead to amplification of source levels. For correct choice of regularization parameter that serves as an input to Tikhonov regularization, a new approach is devised. The new parameter estimation method is based on suitable choice of singular value, calculated from decomposing transfer function matrix that links measurement and source plane data, which serves a best trade-off for effective localization and amplitude quantification. This study aims to correctly localize and quantify a sound source of interest by solving the inverse problem associated with NAH. The work presents a novel approach to tackle ill-conditioning associated with data inversion by choosing a suitable regularization parameter for avoiding deterioration of solution matrix. This method is compared with existing and widely used parameter estimation methods like Generalized Cross Validation (GCV) and L-Curve and found to perform well if both localization and quantification is of interest.

1. Introduction

Phased array techniques have been in focus for over several decades, owing to its transmission and reception capabilities for source detection and navigation. Phased array techniques are so called because data acquisition is carried out simultaneously by the multiple in-phase sensors in an array. The scope of phased array techniques is very broad, catering from a low frequency acoustic application to a high frequency ultrasonic one. Acoustic source localization is one such application which is the focus of this work.

In noise related problems, Transfer path analysis (source-path-receiver) is widely used concept in many industries like automobile, aviation etc. Many a times troubleshooting is done by working on either source or path. The source is firstly tried to work upon and bring down to its lowest level, to then work upon various transfer paths. To mitigate or control the noise levels of source (e.g. engine) using passive or active treatment, correct characterization of dominant areas to work on are to be known. This calls for introduction of special techniques to localize and quantify a sound source to describe its acoustic radiation. Extensive usage of these localization techniques using phased array of microphones is carried out in automobile and aviation industry. In the present work, one such localization technique namely planar-NAH technique for source localization is under consideration. With its basic foundation laid down by Maynard et al.[1], NAH technique is optimized over time based on the nature of sources and applications. Veronesi and Maynard [2] gave the computational basis to NAH algorithm by approximating and assuming some necessary conditions to reduce the infinite and continuous convolution integrals to a finite and discrete form. In the discretized formulation, the data is collected by a grid of microphones on the measurement plane and then back propagated on to source plane to derive source characteristics. Hence NAH analysis by its very nature is setup as an inverse problem which is bound to ill-conditioning owing to smaller singular values associated with noise. This problem is tackled using the knowledge of regularization which along with proper parameter estimation method effectively treats the data matrix and correctly characterizes the source information. The most widely used method for matrix regularization is Tikhonov based formulation. Regularization depends critically on the choice of regularization parameter. A high value of regularization parameter results in loss of the information about the source, on the other hand, a small value causes the results to blow-up. To have a correct choice of regularization parameter for proper matrix conditioning, Generalized Cross Validation (GCV) [3] and L-Curve [4] are the two most widely used techniques. However in this work, a new parameter estimation method is proposed to significantly improve the localization and quantification of sound source.

2. Setup and measurements:

The setup shown in Fig.1 depicts stepwise data capturing and processing using calibrated instruments. The acoustic data in all the experiments are captured using quarter inch, omni-directional electret condenser microphones (Kingstate model KECG3642TFA) which have almost flat spectral response in the audible range (100 Hz to 20 kHz) with an uncertainty of ± 3 dB. These microphones are calibrated using a Brüel and Kjær pistonphone (model 4228) which is a single point frequency calibrator (250 Hz and 124 dB). A 20 mm diameter iBall LIL BOMB70 bluetooth mini speaker having a diaphragm diameter 20 mm is used as a sound source during experiments. It has directional characteristics at higher frequencies, but results are processed only up to a frequency of 7500 Hz for which directionality of source is not much dominant. Localization is done for various frequencies played through speaker with sampling frequency of 25 kHz. A 5x5 configuration planar array with spacing of 15 mm between consecutive microphones in both orthogonal directions is used in this setup framing a square array of dimension of 60x60 mm. The microphones are linked to a terminal board and then to the Data Acquisition (DAQ) device which is operated using a computer. Agilent U2331A USB modular multifunction data acquisition device is used for capturing and acquiring acoustic data. The system has 32 differential inputs and can sample data upto 1 million samples per second, with a 12-bit Analog to Digital Converter (ADC). A similar setup is tuned for simulation study to validate experimental work but instead of a speaker source, a point source or a monopole source is generated using standard formulations [5]. Post processing [6] of these data is carried out using licensed Matlab R2015a version.

Figure 1. Experimental and data acquisition setup

A green marker is used in simulation and experimental Sound Pressure Level (SPL) plots to indicate the actual source location and dimension. In simulation since a point source has to be indicated a very small marker is used. For convenience, reconstruction (source to measurement plane) distance is always denoted in accordance with microphone spacing. dx is universally used for denoting microphone spacing in both X and Y direction because in this work microphone spacing in both directions is same.

3. Mathematical Formulation

3.1 Planar NAH

The equation for pressure wave in the frequency domain is given by the Helmholtz equation

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{p}(\vec{r}, \omega) + k^2(\omega) \mathbf{p}(\vec{r}, \omega) = \mathbf{0} \quad (1)$$

Here, $k = \omega/c$. The sources are confined to the plane $z = 0$. Since the geometry of the domain is rectangular, we can decompose the waves into planar waves. Taking an waveform representation as $p(x, y, 0, t) = A_0 e^{i(k_x x + k_y y - \omega t)}$, we get a solution to the Helmholtz equation,

$$\mathbf{p}(x, y, z, t) = A_0 e^{i(k_x x + k_y y + (\sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2})z - \omega t)}. \quad (2)$$

This implies $k_z = \sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}$. By superimposing the waves, we get the solution to our problem to be the following

$$\mathbf{p}(x, y, z, \omega) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \int d\mathbf{k}_x d\mathbf{k}_y \mathbf{p}_0(\mathbf{k}_x, \mathbf{k}_y) e^{i(k_x x + k_y y + (\sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2})z)} \quad (3)$$

where, $p_0(k_x, k_y)$ is amplitude of the wave on the source plane. Note that if $k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2$ is negative, we get an imaginary value of k_z implying that the amplitude of the wave decays exponentially with the distance from the source plane. Such waves are called evanescent waves. This is, however, a continuum formulation of the problem. For the practical purposes, we need a discretized version, which follows :

The pressure data in a matrix form on the measurement plane, p_M is related to the pressure on the source plane, p_S by the following equation

$$\mathbf{F} p_M = \mathbf{G}_p (\mathbf{F} p_S) \quad (4)$$

where, F is the spatial Fourier transform matrix and G_p is the pressure propagator. Equation (3) and (4) implies that G_p is a diagonal matrix with elements $e^{i(\sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2})z}$. Thus, $p_M = \mathbf{H}_p p_S$, where $\mathbf{H}_p = \mathbf{F}^{-1} \mathbf{G}_p \mathbf{F}$.

Now, we get p_S from p_M by simply inverting H_p . However, corresponding to the evanescent waves, H_p has singular values of the form $e^{-k'_z z}$, which are very small because of the exponential decay with distance. This results in blow-up of the results after the inversion of H_p . To overcome this problem, we need the mathematical tool of regularization.

3.2 Regularization

3.2.1 Singular Value Decomposition

Any matrix A can be decomposed as $A = U\Sigma V^\dagger = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{u}_i \sigma_i \mathbf{v}_i^\dagger$, where U and V are unitary matrices and Σ is a diagonal matrix containing singular values. Thus, the solution of the equation $A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}$ is given by $\mathbf{x} = \sum_{i=1}^n (\mathbf{u}_i^\dagger \mathbf{b}) (1/\sigma_i) \mathbf{v}_i$. Since the singular values appear in the denominator, the solution blows up because of the presence of small singular values.

3.2.2 Tikhonov Regularization

To tackle the issue of blow-up we redefine the problem as follows

$$\mathbf{x}_\lambda = \operatorname{argmin}\{\|A\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{b}\|_2^2 + \lambda^2 \|L\mathbf{x}\|_2^2\} \quad (5)$$

where L is a regularization matrix which we assume to be identity. Solution to equation (5) follows:

$$\mathbf{x} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\sigma_i^2}{\sigma_i^2 + \lambda_i^2} (\mathbf{u}_i^\dagger \mathbf{b}) (1/\sigma_i) \mathbf{v}_i$$

For $\sigma_i \ll \lambda$, filter $f_i = \sigma_i^2 / (\sigma_i^2 + \lambda_i^2)$ is effectively 0, whereas for $\sigma_i \gg \lambda$, $f_i \sim 1$. The nature of the solution depends on the choice of regularization parameter. Small value of λ causes the solution to blow-up whereas a large value is responsible for over-smoothing of the solution. The correct choice is done using a new parameter estimation formulation instead of existing methods.

3.3 A Novel Method for Parameter Estimation

In this work, a novel method of parameter selection is devised. By analysing the existing parameter estimation methods it was clear that most of the methods tend to select the value of α based on knowledge of singular values obtained from SVD of transfer function matrix. But correct selection of α was a point of concern in this study since both the best methods namely GCV and L-Curve seemed to not work well for this study. Hence a plot of singular values as seen in Fig.2 for different frequencies and stand-off distances are studied and it was observed that correct value of α that maintained a proper balance between over-smoothed and unregularized solution always seemed to be a point of maximum curvature. Owing to which, a new method is proposed. This proposed new method helps us in maintaining a perfect balance between localization and degree of blowup of source strength thus improving the quality of result. It basically chooses a singular value having maximum curvature as shown in Fig. 2 to be used as parameter α which serves as input for Tikhonov regularization.

For a curve $y = f(\sigma)$, where σ indicates singular values and if it is plotted with respect to number of measurement points (x -direction), then it is seen that with an increase in x , curve tends to steep down. It is a concave up curve of generic form $y' < 0$ and $y'' < 0$ for which maximum curvature can be estimated as $(\alpha) = \frac{y''}{[1+(y')^2]^{3/2}}$. This method is seen to perform better than GCV and L-curve in this experimental setup of acoustic related problem. This is a proper study explaining parameter estimation method specifically for acoustic problem.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Ill-conditioning and Regularization:

The SPL maps plotted in Fig.3 highlights the importance of regularization to treat ill-conditioned data matrix to correctly localize a source and also illustrates effectiveness of parameter estimation method to control source strength over-prediction or amplification seen in non-regularized data on comparison with regularized data. It is seen that even at smaller stand-off distances of 1.0 dx, data is

Figure 2. Generic form of singular value plot

ill-conditioned due to inversion of smaller singular value owing to amplification of noise which in turn dominates source levels.

Figure 3. SPL plots for Ill-conditioned, non-regularized and regularized data for 2000 Hz at 1.0 dx.

The simulation and experimental plots in Fig.4 justifies the level of source amplification and helps understand the degree of ill-conditioning of data matrix with respect to reconstruction distance for different frequencies. It was observed that with respect to stand-off distance the ill-conditioning increased exponentially thus amplifying source levels as seen in Fig.4. In the Fig.4 (a), the amplitude suppression owing to regularization for both simulation and experimental data is shown for various frequencies. The condition number of data matrix before and after regularization is shown in Fig.4 (b) which tends to show the effectiveness of data treatment. If observed in linear scale, that matrix conditioning is done as a factor of 10 for simulation and 100 for experimental data by account of which a proper localization and quantification of source is made possible.

Figure 4. Simulation and Experimental result depicting (a) Mean pressure and (b) Condition number plot

4.2 Comparison between New method, GCV and L-Curve:

4.2.1 Source localization map:

SPL contour plots are processed using different algorithms namely New modified method, GCV and L-Curve for simulation and experimental study are illustrated in Fig. 5 and 6. It is observed in both simulation and experiment that localization is of almost equal order when it comes to all methods, but quantification seems to vary which is depicted in acoustic maps. It can be seen that the amplitude values for L-Curve are much beyond what is predicted by other two methods. It can be stated that GCV tends to provide a good localization map with slight source amplitude under-prediction by 2-4 dB whereas L-Curve highly over-predicted the source level by 15-20 dB.

Figure 5. Simulation : SPL plot comparing 3 methods at $z_h-z_s=1.0$ dx and 2000 Hz

Figure 6. Experiment: SPL plot comparing 3 methods at $z_h-z_s=1.0$ dx and 2000 Hz

To justify the effectiveness of the new method, a more detailed parametric analysis involving localization error, mean pressure and dynamic range with respect to frequency for a reconstruction distance of 1.0 dx is done in Fig.7. Since experimental results showed a similar trend, only simulation results are plotted to justify the theory.

Figure 7. Parametric study: (a) Mean pressure, (b) localization error and (c) dynamic range

The parametric study comparing all three methods with respect to frequency is illustrated in Fig. 7. The mean pressure plot (a) of Fig.7 shows a accurate prediction of mean amplitude level of source using new method where GCV and L-Curve method are seen to under-predict or over-predict the levels accordingly. The localization error plot (b) of Fig.7 for new method is on par with GCV method till 2000 Hz after which a good improvement is seen for higher frequencies till 10000 Hz. This can be verified by noise level suppression owing to reduction of singular value inversion seen at frequencies above 2000 Hz. The dynamic range is improved by 1 dB than GCV prediction as seen from dynamic range plot (c) of Fig.7. Hence an overall improvement in terms of all parameters is seen and so it is concluded that new method worked better than GCV and L-Curve in this research.

4.2.2 Parameter selection:

Figure 8. Choice of parameter α by New method, GCV and L-curve for 1000 Hz at 1.0 dx

Table 1. Simulation : 1.0 dx

Frequency(Hz)	GCV	L-Curve	New Modified method
200	1.00	0.012	0.21
500	1.00	0.012	0.21
1000	1.00	0.012	0.213
2000	1.00	0.012	0.23
5000	0.99	0.015	0.24
10000	0.99	0.03	0.45

Table 2. Experimental : 1.0 dx

Frequency(Hz)	GCV	L-Curve	New Modified method
200	1.00	0.012	0.21
500	1.00	0.012	0.21
1000	1.00	0.012	0.213
2000	1.00	0.012	0.23
5000	0.99	0.015	0.24
7500	0.99	0.019	0.351

To justify the choice of parameter α discussed in section 3.3 by new method, GCV and L-curve, Fig.8 is plotted. It can be clearly seen that GCV tends to choose tail value (close to unity) and L-curve prefers head value (close to zero) of the curve. To get more insights with respect to different frequencies for a particular stand-off distance, Tables 4.1 and 4.2 are shown highlighting α value predicted using the new modified method in comparison with GCV and L-Curve. As studied in Eqn.5, value of α greater than or equal to unity mathematically reflects that too much weightage is given to the second term in equation and hence over smoothness is introduced. And, if α value chosen is zero, mathematically it means that there is no filtering done to the solution norm in Eqn.5 and hence the solution obtained is an unregularized one. On the other hand, it can be seen that the proposed method selected a correct choice of α that seemed to maintain a proper balance between over-smoothed and unregularized solution.

5. Conclusion

It can be concluded that the new method for estimating parameter α used in regularization of the inverse problem is better than the existing method like L-Curve and at par with GCV in terms of localization efficiency with slight source strength under-prediction of 2-3 dB. It can be seen that the new method localized and quantified the sound source effectively with less than 5% error. The spatial resolution and dynamic range were also seen to be well above compared existing methods thus improving quality of plotted result. In similar test and simulation conditions where new method correctly characterized the sound source, L-curve and GCV underperformed. It can be concluded that the choice of parameter α using a proposed method seemed to maintain a proper balance between over-smoothed and unregularized solution leading to proper localization and quantification of sound sources.

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